

Case Study 7: Data trust, sharing & preservation

Colin Bird, Samantha Kanza, Nicola Knight, Cerys Willoughby, Jeremy Frey, Simon Coles
School of Chemistry, Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Southampton,
Southampton, SO17 1BJ

Case Study Outline

The main aims of this case study were to

- Explore the need for and the possible form of a data trust and a sharing framework for applicability to PSDI.
- Develop recommendations for preservation and curation approaches.

This was achieved by

- (a) Evaluating existing frameworks and concepts for data trusts and defining the relevant concepts that need to be considered for a data trust.
- (b) Consulting with the initial PSDI community, as identified in the Statement of Need, along with the other PSDI Phase 1 case studies.

We explored the perception of trust in data, what aspects provide this trust, what mechanisms currently exist to provide and support trust and whether a more formal data trust framework is needed in the physical sciences and if necessary how this could be implemented.

1 Background & Motivation

The further we advance into the 21st century, the more science becomes data-driven or, as Hey et al put it, data-intensive. They recognised the significance of the change that data had wrought for modern science in the title of their book, *The Fourth Paradigm*¹. While the Physical Sciences have been in the forefront of the recognition that for data to be reliably usable and reusable, certain attributes are required, hence the publication of “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship” in *Nature Scientific Data*², there is still much to be done to achieve an open and trusted science environment.

The future of scientific discovery depends on the reuse of shared and exchanged data; even full compliance with the foundational principles will not suffice: FAIR data is not axiomatically trustworthy, an issue to which this report will return. If, like Isaac Newton, we are to see “further by standing on the shoulders [sic] of Giants”³, we have to be able to depend on those shoulders.

Willoughby analyses the history and current direction of research data management in Chapter 5 of her book “Recording Science in the Digital Era”⁴, noting that the traditional

method of disseminating research findings is an unreliable way to reuse or reproduce the science. As Physical Science research grows in both scale and complexity, very large quantities of data are generated but we cannot afford either the time or the funds to repeat work already done. We must make the best possible use of data that already exists, which means becoming significantly more effective and efficient about sharing and exchanging extant data. This obligation is particularly pertinent for those problems that need urgent solutions.

Experimental data generated in the Physical Sciences is now almost exclusively “born digital”, but the preservation of that data does not always meet the standards required for other researchers to reuse that data confidently. In particular, the necessary metadata to establish not only the nature of the data but also its reliability and provenance is often missing.

On pages 95-96 of her book, Willoughby lists questions that might (indeed should?) need to be answered when compiling a Data Management Plan:⁵

- *What is the nature of the data?*
- *How will the data be collected?*
- *Are there any issues of copyright or intellectual property rights with the data?*
- *Are there any ethical issues associated with the data; is it sensitive or private?*
- *How will licensing and consent for the data be handled?*
- *What volumes will be generated?*
- *How will the data be processed?*
- *What format will it be captured in?*
- *What formats are most suitable for sharing in your community?*
- *What metadata will be captured?*
- *Will standard or interchangeable formats be used?*
- *How will quality be ensured?*
- *How will the data be secured and backed-up?*
- *What are the risks to the data and what disaster recovery procedures are in place?*
- *How will the data be organised and managed?*
- *How will the data be shared?*
- *Where will it be archived and how will archive data be selected?*
- *How will the data be citable?*
- *How long will it be retained?*
- *How will unwanted data be disposed of?*
- *Who has responsibility for the different stages and tasks in the process?*

If we adjust these questions to use the past tense, almost all of them could be asked legitimately by other researchers aspiring to reuse the data. If what we know about the data answers our key questions adequately, we can be confident that the data is trustworthy.

The next step is to consider the mechanism(s) whereby prospective data users can connect to compliant providers. The channels will need to take account not only the scale and complexity of both the science and the data it generates but also the emergence of aggregations: science is now highly collaborative, and consortia can be responsible for data from a number of institutions.

The PSDI vision recognises that each endeavour in Physical Science builds its own data infrastructure and that those resources should remain dedicated to the specific application⁶. The aim of the PSDI infrastructure layer is to create a trusted environment that connects those assets and enables them to be shared.

1.1 Relationships in Data Exchanges

Sound relationships are essential for effective scientific collaboration and in many cases joint research involved the exchange of data and materials on a peer-to-peer basis, where a ‘peer’ might in practice be an individual or a group. The ever-increasing scale and complexity of projects and the data that they generate has perhaps led to a preference for creating fresh data rather than reusing data that already exists. That preference might also be influenced by a decline in trust, owing to the perceived ‘crisis’ of reproducibility revealed by the survey reported by Nature in 2016⁷. The impact of such concerns is, however, not clear-cut, in that the article reports “a confusing snapshot of attitudes”, although, of the survey respondents:

73% said that they think that at least half of the papers in their field can be trusted, with physicists and chemists generally showing the most confidence.

1.2 The Need for Change

The PSDI vision recognises that there are numerous data-centric infrastructures supporting UK research in the Physical Sciences. While these centralised infrastructures are trusted within their specific communities, the aim of PSDI is to connect these collections into a “socio-technical data infrastructure” that extends trust across domains and between facilities.

It is unquestionable that the FAIR Principles will apply, so the purpose of this case study is to investigate the options for building a trusted mechanism for making data available across the infrastructure. We therefore require a system or procedure for sharing information and content from highly curated, FAIR-compliant collections. Ultimately, the sharing is likely to be on the peer-to-peer basis referred to above, subject to some form of contractual relationship, which might or might not be formalised.

Put simply, data (re)users will need to know what it is they are working with, and so will expect to be able to trust the stewardship and curation of the data provided. In some instances, this trust is already very well established. For example, the Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) and the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC)⁸ are highly respected.

One objective could be to raise the level of trust across the whole PSDI infrastructure to a level comparable to that enjoyed by the CSD, which implies a requirement to devise a mechanism for sharing and exchanging that embodies trust. To quote from the CoreTrustSeal Requirements⁹.

If we want to be able to share data, we need to store them in a trustworthy data repository.

The title of this case study includes the term “Data Trust”. Section 2 of this report examines existing frameworks and trusts, including the legal implications of establishing a formal trust.

1.3 Data Trusts

The Open Data Institute (ODI) describes data trusts as follows¹⁰:

Data trusts are an approach to looking after and making decisions about data in a similar way that trusts have been used to look after and make

decisions about other forms of asset in the past, such as land trusts that steward land on behalf of local communities.

The Wikitia Data trust page further explains the concept¹¹.

Our preliminary survey of the literature relating to data trusts in the science context gives the impression that there is rather more material about the principles of data trusts (DTs) and what their use involves and implies than there is describing actual trusts operating in practice. However, there are commercial examples. Indeed, a group of commercial lawyers express the view that most DTs will operate in the commercial arena¹².

1.3.1 Data Trust Principles

The authors of¹² trace the emergence of data trusts as a means to facilitate data sharing to the Hall and Pesenti review, *Growing the UK AI Industry*¹³, in which the top recommendation was that:

Government and industry should deliver a programme to develop Data Trusts – proven and trusted frameworks and agreements – to ensure exchanges are secure and mutually beneficial.

In its Executive Summary, the review recommends:

- Development of data trusts, to improve trust and ease around sharing data
- Making more research data machine readable
- Supporting text and data mining as a standard and essential tool for research.

The review does not delve deeply into the anatomy of trust frameworks, but the FSA report¹⁴ is more forthcoming in that respect:

In a commercial context a decentralised approach is more realistic, with data retained by the owners in their own distributed data stores and mediated by a body that eases the exchange without seeing the data itself. The concept of a trust framework builds on the principles behind the data trust by accepting these commercial realities, focusing on lowering the barriers for secure information exchange and empowering new forms of collaboration. Rather than collating static, passive data collections, trust frameworks allow for the possibility of monitoring and sampling flows of information both within and between organisations.

Lawrence et al¹⁵ see trust frameworks as a means for delegating their rights and responsibilities for data to stewards who administer data access on their behalf. With regard to the nature of trusts in practice, Lawrence says: "it's not a one-size-fits-all".

Being abstract governance mechanisms, the forms that data trusts take rarely dictate how data are physically stored; instead "data trusts work by centralising rights, not the data itself"

The trust principles for digital repositories are also considered in a 2020 Nature article¹⁶.

The legal aspects of data trusts and their governance have been considered fully in the context of food data trusts¹⁴. Closer examination of this document and any issues that might arise from it are arguably best left for a later stage of Case Study 7.

1.3.2 Data Trust Requirements

In 2020, the ODI published *Designing trustworthy data institutions*¹⁷, a comprehensive report about research into sustainable data institutions, based on establishing an ecosystem of trust. The report considers the implications for stakeholders and what is required for the ecosystem to be sustainable.

In 2021, the ODI also published – as a work in progress - a guidebook for trustworthy data stewardship¹⁸.

Paprica et al, publishing in the International Journal of Population Data Science¹⁹, propose twelve minimum specification requirements for a data trust. The primary requirement is Legal, four requirements relate to Governance, three to Management, and two each to Data users and to “Public and stakeholder engagement”.

Element AI and Nesta have published a policy white paper resulting from a December 2018 International Workshop on Data Trusts²⁰. The incentive for this workshop was the growing concern about the poor control that individuals have over the use and misuse of their data, causing a decline in public trust.

One of the goals of the workshop was to leverage the wide-ranging expertise from invited speakers and contributors to co-develop appropriate and practical data governance solutions that are fit for the future, have global relevance and can be tested today.

The motivations for this workshop, the perceived lack of confidence in the mechanisms for control of data, digital rights, and intellectual property should apply equally well in the PSDI context. The white paper covers three use cases: Urban data (improving the urban environment); Health data (gathering sensitive information for research purposes); and Data from online platforms (specifically the use of ride-sharing data for urban planning). One of the conclusions asserts that the “concept of ownership is not easily applicable to data”, a point that PSDI might need to consider.

Kieron O’Hara (Web Science Institute) also published a 27-page white paper at around the same time, entitled *Data Trusts Ethics, Architecture and Governance for Trustworthy Data Stewardship*²¹. This paper seems to cover both the issues and the practical considerations in a comprehensive and easily digested manner. The Architecture section is of particular interest. It lists seven desirable properties: Discovery; Provenance; Access Controls; Access; Identity management; Auditing of use; and Impact. O’Hara also provides a diagram depicting a Data Trust Portal (DTP), which potentially looks useful.

1.3.3 Food Data Trust

At the outset of the PSDI pilot project the work of the EPSRC Internet of Food Things DE Network+, working with the Food Standards Agency (FSA) in the area of data trusts, was a motivating example of the type of structures that could be used as a model for data trusts in PSDI. That Network+ developed a trust framework for digital food systems²².

The University of Lincoln and the FSA issued a report, referred to subsequently as the *FSA report*⁴⁴, in which the *opportunity* section refers to “mechanisms to monitor and measure”; access to specific items of information; “a more targeted, risk-based approach to inspections”; and speedier exchange when incidents related to the fresh produce sector require an urgent response. Brewer et al²² note that:

Data exchanges can orchestrate critical network dependencies, define standards and underpin food safety.

Clearly, these motivations are appropriate to food safety, but are the PSDI requirements more about maximising scientific utility and building on the results of other projects?

Notwithstanding any motivational divergence, two quotes from the *Introduction* to the FSA report show the commonality in the overarching rationale:

How do independent, competing but cooperating organisations choose to make information accessible to each other in a way that is safe, legally valid and demonstrably beneficial? How can building the trust necessary for such exchange be made swifter and simpler?

Data trusts, and more specifically trust frameworks, offer a mechanism to manage decentralised and distributed collections of data that are temporarily linked in limited and specific ways, so that information can be shared securely.

2 Existing Frameworks & Concepts

The areas covered in our examination of existing frameworks that are – or could be – relevant to data sharing and preservation for the Physical Sciences were loosely classified as follows:

- *“Gleams in the eye”*: discussions of the issues
- *Specifications* (ranging from conceptual to formal)
- *Architectures and design briefs*
- *Working systems* (including prototypes)

An additional section, *FAIRmat / NOMAD Overview*, covers the FAIRmat/NOMAD infrastructure in greater detail.

2.1 “Gleams in the eye”: discussions of the issues

2.1.1 Open Data Institute (ODI)

No framework(s) as such are described, but plenty of articles discuss the issues in depth. The article *Data trusts in 2020*²³ looks to be a good starting point.

2.1.2 Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP)

In March 2021, CSaP (University of Cambridge) published a guide to the role of data trusts in data governance¹⁵.

2.1.3 Materials 4.0

It might seem harsh to place this EPSRC “big idea” in this category, but the Landscaping Report produced by the Henry Royce Institute is (amongst other topics) about enabling trust in data exchange²⁴. This report discusses technologies that might be suitable for building trust and credibility. The seven Case Studies all employ systems that do not involve a central trusted party and use distributed ledger technology:

Using appropriate technologies, such as distributed ledgers, identities or file systems inherently helps to build trust and credibility between parties within the ecosystem.

The Digital Sandwich case study states that it uses the FSA Data Trust Framework (see below), but it is not immediately obvious how that Framework was implemented.

2.2 Specifications (ranging from conceptual to formal)

2.2.1 CoreTrustSeal

The CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements were developed by a working group of the Research Data Alliance²⁵ asserting that certification could contribute to ensuring the reliability and durability of data repositories, thus ensuring the longer-term prospects for data sharing.

Certification can be an important contribution to ensuring the reliability and durability of data repositories and hence the potential for sharing data over a long period of time. By becoming certified, repositories can demonstrate to both their users and their funders that an independent authority has evaluated them and endorsed their trustworthiness.

The certification process entails a repository completing a self-assessment.

2.2.2 FSA Food Data Trust

The research project funded by the Food Standards Agency (FSA) completed in March 2021¹⁴. In July 2021, Recommendation 12 in the Independent Review of the National Food Strategy²⁶ was:

The Government should create a National Food System Data Programme to collect and share data, so that the businesses and other organisations involved in the food system can track progress and plan ahead.

However, a data trust as such was not mentioned.

2.3 Architectures and design briefs

In 2020, the ODI published *Designing trustworthy data institutions*¹⁷, a comprehensive report about research into sustainable data institutions, based on establishing an ecosystem of trust. The report considers the implications for stakeholders and what is required for the ecosystem to be sustainable.

In 2019, Kieron O'Hara (Web Science Institute) published a 27-page white paper entitled *Data Trusts Ethics, Architecture and Governance for Trustworthy Data Stewardship*²¹.

In 2018, at the Fifteenth Annual Acquisition Research Symposium, Talburt presented *A Review of Trusted Broker Architectures for Data Sharing*²⁷.

2.4 Working systems (including prototypes)

2.4.1 NOMAD Repository and Archive (plus FAIRmat)

According to reference²⁸, NOMAD was founded to provide open access to scientific materials data, enabling sharing and reuse. NOMAD is a centralised system:

All data is available in their raw format as produced by the underlying code (Repository) and in a common, machine-processable, and well-defined data

format (Archive). Data can be downloaded and used under the CC-BY-4.0 license.

2.4.1.1 FAIRmat

Further investigation reveals that FAIRmat is the infrastructure for managing the full lifecycle of materials science data, from preservation to publication. FAIRmat adheres to FAIR Principles and is based on NOMAD, which manages workload in a distributed system by providing an interface between applications and the operating system.

As FAIRmat is easily the nearest “role model” for what we currently understand PSDI would be looking to provide, notwithstanding its focus on computational materials science data, the additional section *FAIRmat / NOMAD Overview* examines this infrastructure in greater detail.

2.4.2 Legal perspective

The Lexology report¹² lists four examples of data trusts and DTFs (data trust frameworks), each outlined below.

2.4.3 Silicon Valley Regional Data Trust (SVRDT)

SVRDT is a Center for Collaborative Research for an Equitable California (CCREC) project²⁹, but the page cited gives no technical information. Checking what other sources suggest its official website to be – www.svrdt.org – was unsuccessful, as that site appears not to exist.

2.4.4 Trūata

The full name looks to be Trūata Anonymization Service (TAS), an independent trust set up by IBM and Mastercard to enable businesses to comply with the EU GDPR regulations³⁰. Although we were unable to uncover any technical information, it looks as though the trust functions as an intermediary between data controllers in separate organisations.

2.4.5 SITA BagTrust

SITA (Société Internationale de Télécommunications Aéronautiques) provides a baggage handling system based on a form of data trust³¹. However, SITA appear not to be using the term *BagTrust*.

Access to the data is controlled by a rules-based system:

What we'll provide here is a set of rules allowing airlines and airports to identify what data can be shared and who can see it. This involves a trust mechanism to underpin all the capabilities around data sharing.

2.4.6 WildLabs Tech Hub

Looks like an ODI pilot project, setting up a data trust for sharing information relating to the illegal wildlife trade³².

2.4.7 Data exchanges

The following exchange systems appear to be localised and comparatively small-scale. DAWEX might be the exception, although the impression given is that each DAWEX setup would be for an individual organisation.

2.4.7.1 SPECCHIO

The SPECCHIO database system enables data exchange between distributed spectral databases³³.

2.4.7.2 World Meteorological Organization (WMO)

The WMO Information System (WIS) is a cloud-based infrastructure that, amongst other functions, facilitates data exchange³⁴.

2.4.7.3 DANS, the Data Archiving and Networked Services institute of The Netherlands

DANS is adaptable in that it can manage data from a range of domains³⁵.

2.4.7.4 DAWEX

DAWEX is a comprehensive data exchange platform for setting up and managing data ecosystem; the term data marketplace is also used³⁶.

2.5 FAIRmat / NOMAD Overview

NOMAD is an acronym for NOvel MAterials Discovery. The NOMAD website²⁸ also has a tab for FAIRmat.

2.5.1 NOMAD

From the NOMAD introductory video²⁸:

NOMAD is an open data sharing platform for materials science data based on FAIR principles.

What makes NOMAD unique, in contrast to other platforms that just use user-provided metadata to organise the data, is that NOMAD processes all data and extracts rich, materials-science-specific metadata.

All data that is provided to NOMAD is stored in its original form in the NOMAD Repository.

The NOMAD Repository holds all the raw data, which is parsed into a common representation and held in the NOMAD Archive. The indications are that NOMAD is intended for computational data (rather than the variety that PSDI might expect):

At the moment, the NOMAD Repository contains the input and output files of almost 11 million code runs that were performed by many popular computational materials science codes.

2.5.1.1 NOMAD Oasis

The Oasis option enables a user to run an independent local server, which provides all the functions in the NOMAD toolkit and can be synchronised with the central NOMAD server³⁷.

2.5.2 FAIRmat

FAIRmat is a consortium funded by the German Research-Data Infrastructure (NFDI)³⁸. The long description of the consortium is:

FAIR Data Infrastructure for Condensed-Matter Physics and the Chemical Physics of Solids

While the emphasis for FAIRmat is clearly on computational materials science, its objectives would be applicable more broadly³⁹:

- *create a federated FAIR DI for materials data with a central hub, the FAIRmat Portal;*
- *advance and develop metadata schemas and ontologies;*
- *enable efficient exchange of the FAIR research data, ensuring that the FAIRmat DI will advance basic science of condensed-matter and materials physics with very little burden for active researchers and also be of great value for engineering;*
- *convince scientists to also share data they consider useless for their present purpose-oriented research;*
- *reach out within and beyond its community providing advice, training, and user support.*

FAIRmat's structure covers seven areas; Area D - Data Infrastructure:

will lay the foundation for a federated research data infrastructure for the wider condensed-matter and chemical-physics community.

2.5.2.1 Data quality

The quality and veracity of the data stored in NOMAD for FAIRmat appears to be somewhat taken for granted, conceivably owing to the reliance on FAIR principles. Appraisal of the overviews for two of the pillars around which FAIRmat is organised shows that the assurance of veracity relies on standards and rigorous policies.

From the Heterogeneous Catalysis⁴⁰:

... definition of standards and clear procedures is necessary, which will enable quality control and the collection of reliable and balanced datasets that are then amenable to modern data analytics.

From the Experimental Materials Science pillar⁴¹:

The data generation must be transparent, comprehensible and repeatable so that a quality assurance, traceability or reusability of the data becomes possible.

2.6 Concept definitions (in alphabetical order)

2.6.1 Broker (Trusted Broker)

Curiously, definitions of a *trusted broker for data sharing* are in short supply. It is somewhat surprising that Frey and Bird did not attempt to define a trusted broker in their trading perspective paper⁴², other than indirectly by describing the functionality.

From Bhargava et al⁴³: a trusted third party responsible for maintaining end-to-end auditing in a chain of information flow upon the request of a client business process.

The role we might envisage is possibly more akin to that of a message broker⁴⁴:

A message broker is software that enables applications, systems, and services to communicate with each other and exchange information.

The definitions for a *data broker* indicate that the concept of an individual or organisation that collects data for selling or licensing to other organisations is distinct from the concept of a trusted broker at the hub of a data exchange.

Tentative suggestion:

An independent organisation that provides data sharing services between two or more otherwise independent parties, while ensuring that the objects of all such transactions can be trusted by both the data owner and the data user. If PSDI were to serve as a trusted broker, it should be independent of any party to an exchange.

2.6.2 Data Economy

Adopting the Wikipedia definition⁴⁵, but substituting the term *providers* for *vendors*:

A data economy is a global digital ecosystem in which data is gathered, organized, and exchanged by a network of providers for the purpose of deriving value from the accumulated information.

2.6.3 Data Exchange

Broadly speaking, there are three meanings:

- a) the process whereby one party provides data to a second party, essentially on a peer-to-peer basis;
- b) the infrastructure that enables the process of exchanging data;
- c) the conversion of data from one format to a different format.

Perhaps we need two definitions, as follows:

2.6.3.1 Data Exchange Process

The process whereby one party provides data to a second party, essentially on a peer-to-peer basis.

2.6.3.2 Data Exchange Infrastructure

The infrastructure that enables the process of exchanging or sharing data between parties.

2.6.4 Data Marketplace

Generally, 'data marketplace' is used to describe a place for buying and selling third-party data, typically commercial data, so we might not need to include a definition for this concept.

2.6.5 Data Sharing

In their trading perspective paper, Frey and Bird made the following observation about terminologies⁴²:

In the context of scientific collaboration, the terms sharing and exchange are used almost interchangeably, thereby disregarding the wider understanding that exchange involves receiving something in return, whereas sharing might be more altruistic. Such distinctions often become blurred, in that sharing can be mutual and exchanged items are not necessarily equivalent in value. In the scientific research context specifically, neither sharing nor exchange involves an explicit assumption of receiving assets in return, apart from a reliance that proper attribution, such as citation, will be given.

Tentative suggestion:

The process whereby one party provides data on a broad basis, for use by any number of other parties.

2.6.6 Data Trust

From the Open Data Institute (ODI)²³:

A data trust provides independent, fiduciary stewardship of data.

This appears to be their most recent definition, having evolved from earlier versions. Some other sources adopt the ODI definition as the basis for their own.

The ODI article also says that Data trusts represent an approach to stewarding data that can conform to [practices that demonstrate trustworthiness].

From Qlarion⁴⁶:

A data trust is a legal framework for managing shared data. The data trust promotes collaboration among its members through common rules for data security, privacy, and confidentiality. It enables organizations to securely connect their data sources and create a new shared repository of data. The data trust also standardizes and formalizes the relationships between the organizations that are contributing or accessing the data within the repository.

The Qlarion definition, although lengthy, does cover all aspects.

From the Food Data Trust report¹⁴:

Data trusts, and more specifically trust frameworks, offer a mechanism to manage decentralised and distributed collections of data that are temporarily linked in limited and specific ways, so that information can be shared securely.

2.6.7 Distributed ledger

From Wikipedia⁴⁷:

A distributed ledger is a consensus of replicated, shared, and synchronized digital data geographically spread across multiple sites, countries, or institutions. Unlike with a centralized database, there is no central administrator.

Investopedia⁴⁸ adopts a very similar definition. Blockchain is a form of distributed ledger, but other types are available – see article from the Marco Polo Network⁴⁹.

2.6.8 Framework

(As in: framework for data management or data governance)

From Techopedia⁵⁰:

A data governance framework refers to the process of building a model for managing enterprise data.

2.6.9 Stewardship (of data)

The Open Data Institute describes stewardship of data as collecting, maintaining, and sharing it, and in particular, deciding who has access to it, under what conditions and to whose benefit.

2.6.10 Trust (abstract)

From Merriam-Webster⁵¹:

belief that someone or something is reliable, good, honest, effective, etc.

The ODI say that trust and trustworthiness are highly context dependent and that third party assessments are useful, but only to a degree and within certain contexts⁵².

2.6.11 Trust (concrete)

From Merriam-Webster⁵¹:

an arrangement in which someone's property or money is legally held or managed by someone else or by an organization (such as a bank) for usually a set period of time OR an organization that results from the creation of a trust

3 Characteristics required in the PSDI

The scope of the data across the Physical Sciences that might be available for sharing are reuse can be regarded as a *known unknown*. To overcome this invisible barrier, the infrastructure should provide a mechanism or process for connecting prospective users of data with potential providers – groups and/or individuals who are willing to make their data available for sharing and to ensure that their data is FAIR-compliant. This mechanism or process would effectively create an internal data market.

4 Recommendations and Conclusions

The preliminary aim of Case Study 7 was “Explore data trust and sharing framework for applicability to PSDI and develop recommendations for preservation and curation approaches” [As presented to the PSDI All-Partners meeting, 11th January 2022].

During this pilot phase, we have consulted widely through extensive engagement discussions and All-Partners meetings, coupled with literature studies of data trusts in practice, other existing frameworks for supporting data sharing, and the associated concepts. It is apparent that data is now generated at a rate that prohibits the validation carried out historically by organisations such as NIST⁵³. While there is no substitute for thorough review, the 20th century ecosystem involving publication, review, and testing for reproducibility, served the Physical Sciences tolerably well. In the 21st century landscape there is only limited exchange of data, and certainly less than the recognised need for sharing would lead us to expect. The expanding use of machine learning generates a strong demand for more training data, although satisfying that requirement is impeded by the data that might be available not being categorised and compiled. Our conclusion is that the community needs a data sharing ethos that embodies trust, albeit without the formality associated with a data trust.

Currently the community appears not to face the issues of trust and trustworthiness, although there are undoubtedly strong proxies in the form of provenance, reliable metadata, and possibly durability. In the absence of authoritative trust metrics, these proxies underpin the

questions posed when researchers consider reusing data generated outside their own control. While the Open Science movement mitigates the trust issue by closer collaboration, it is implausible to extend such practices across the entire Physical Sciences community. Accordingly, we regard an exploration of the nature of trust in data to be an underpinning aim of this case study.

Reframing Case Study 7 to reflect the required characteristics as now perceived following the pilot study investigations, the aim should become: “[Explore a sharing framework for applicability to PSDI and develop recommendations to provide a mechanism or process, based on trust, for connecting prospective users of data with potential providers.](#)”

Accordingly, the recommendations from the pilot phase of Case Study 7 are as follows:

4.1 Reframe the case study aim to explore a sharing framework such as a data exchange infrastructure

[This recommendation reflects the conclusions of the pilot phase of a study whose original aim was to “Explore data trust and sharing framework for applicability to PSDI ...”](#)

The pilot phase investigation indicated that Data Trusts involve added formal arrangements to some extent at least. Neither All-Partners meetings nor informal engagement discussions have given any affirmative indications that the PSDI community either wants or needs a formal arrangement.

Moreover, there is little evidence of Data Trusts becoming widely established, except in the Commercial Sector, despite the arguments presented in the Hall-Pesenti review¹³.

Although the seven case studies in the Henry Royce Institute Materials 4.0¹³ report do each propose a “Trust/Data Exchange”, none of the seven involve research in the Physical Sciences: broadly speaking, they relate to process management or supply chains. All seven proposed solutions are based on distributed ledgers, which we understand are questionable on energy-consumption grounds (at least).

The emphasis during the pilot phase of this case study therefore shifted to explore how trust and trustworthiness should be integrated into data sharing processes. Accordingly, further recommendations from the pilot phase of Case Study 7 are as follows:

4.2 Preliminary exercise to identify potential requirements for a data exchange and options for providing feedback about shared data.

This comparatively short exercise would look firstly at functional needs, standards, and desirable attributes. Secondly, this exercise would consider comments, suggestions, and assessment options. Both aspects would inform the formulation of the relevant facets of the full consultation.

This preliminary exercise would consider initially the following material:

- Indicators from section 2.3, Architectures and design briefs;
- Insights from All-Partners meetings and informal engagement discussions;

- Specific pointers such as: trust in data and why attitudes appear equivocal; the nature of the provenance information that data (re)users would require; which items of metadata might be deemed essential; and possible ways to encourage people to share their data in the first place.

However, it is important to emphasise the preliminary, and therefore comparatively superficial, nature of this exercise, intended as it is to inform the full consultation.

The ad hoc poll conducted during the AI4SD 2022 Conference indicates that around three-quarters of the 38 respondents have roles requiring them to deal with data that is not under their stewardship and/or preparing data for sharing. The message is somewhat mixed with regard to the trust that respondents have in the data they work with, although more than 55% took a positive view. Uncertainties about trust might be explained by over 80% of respondents saying that knowledge of data provenance is completely or somewhat necessary. More than 70% consider that a data exchange platform would be useful, with the answers regarding desirable features supporting our assessments of the details an exchange infrastructure would require, such as classification, metadata, provenance, quality control, search, semantic information, and standards (in alphabetical order).

4.3 Consult the Physical Sciences community about their data sharing expectations

The objective of this consultation would be to collect information about firm requirements, issues of concern, and features that might not be essential, but would be “nice to have”.

It is apparent from All-Partners meetings, other engagement discussions, and informal conversations that a level of commitment to data sharing exists across the Physical Sciences. Feedback from all eight case studies reveals metadata, standards, integration, and sharing to be common threads. Reliable – trustworthy – metadata is one of the keys to interoperability.

However, before establishing a data exchange mechanism for the PSDI it is vital properly to understand what these incentives mean in practice, hence the proposal for a comprehensive consultation of the Physical Sciences community, with the option subsequently to create a standing forum for reviewing matters relating to data sharing.

The consultation should address the following aspects specifically:

- Understanding of, and expectations regarding, trust and trustworthiness;
- Understanding of provenance and how it should be documented;
- Attitudes, positive and negative, to sharing;
- Metadata standards, particularly the extent to which they can be domain-independent;
- Expectations regarding quality assurance;
- Expectations regarding data durability.

4.4 Engage with the FAIRmat team in Germany

In the short-to-medium term, consider engaging with the FAIRmat team to appreciate how well their arrangements work in practice. The FAIRmat infrastructure appears to rely on a common understanding of what is required of shared data, including the standards that would apply. We recognise that such understanding might be easier for FAIRmat to achieve given its focus on computational materials science data.

4.5 Investigate a data exchange infrastructure

This investigation would be a long-term project, with a general ambition to facilitate a design thinking approach.

The initial phase would involve collecting views about the desirable features of a data exchange, leading into thorough research into the needs of users across the range of Physical Sciences. This phase corresponds to the first stage of the design thinking process, to be followed by generating a portfolio of use cases that would inform the process of creating a high-level architecture and a provisional design brief.

Drawing on the work carried out during this pilot phase, our preliminary – and necessarily provisional – view is that the primary objective of a data exchange would be to make connections between prospective data (re)users and providers, so it would be essentially a finding mechanism. While much of that process could possibly be automated, there are potential advantages to having a ‘trusted broker’ at the core of the exchange mechanism. As well as making connections, the broker could also provide additional functions, for example feedback comprising comments, suggestions, and (maybe) ratings.

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